

Muons Atmospheric Time Dilation

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1 Abstract

After the discovery of unstable particles in the atmosphere, which moves at a speed close to the speed of light and which splits in a fraction of a second when they are at rest, it appeared to the upholders of Einstein Special Relativity theory, that the time of destruction of these particles should be increased strikingly with regard to the one measured in laboratory at rest, due to their high speed.

Thus, if the measurement of the lifetime of these particles was achievable then it would be an excellent validation of Einstein SR theory.

Unstable particles created in the atmosphere by Galactic cosmic rays and solar energetic particles have sufficient energy to counter the Earth geomagnetic field and penetrate in the Earth atmosphere. When they enter into Earth atmosphere they interact with atmospheric atoms and molecules to give a "shower" of unstable particles.

Protons are mostly composing cosmic rays. The interaction between these particles and the nuclei of atoms of the atmosphere produces unstable pions which split also very quickly and produces, in particular, muons which have the peculiarity to have an average lifetime of $2.2 \mu\text{ s}$ measured at rest in a laboratory.

A major experiment on this subject was led by David H. Frisch et James H. Smith of MIT, Cambridge, Massachusetts [1]. This experiment and the results obtained is taught everywhere in schools and universities as being one of the absolute proofs of time dilation predicted by Einstein Special Relativity theory.

2 Experimentation

Here is the introductory summary of this experiment by the authors themselves: *« an experiment was realized to demonstrate that the relativist dilation of time is an important effect and this with relatively simple equipment. Among mesons- m_1 (muons) reaching at the top of the Mount Washington (New Hampshire), those who were selected had to have a speed between $0,9950c$ and $0,9954c$. The number of those who survived to reach the sea level was measured at Cambridge (Massachusetts). The expected number without time dilation was calculated from the distribution of the time of destruction of these mesons- m . (i.e. the life expectancy average) measured as well in this experiment as in others and from the distance known for the descent. The factor observed by the time dilation is $8,8 \pm 0,8$ which must be compared with the factor calculated by effective dilation for mesons having these speeds in the geometry of our system of detection and being worth $1/(1 - v^2/c^2)^{1/2} = 8,4 \pm 2$ ».*

The authors realized an experiment in order to detect muons (or mesons) at two heights: 2000 m (at the top of Mount Washington) and at ground level. Indeed their measures led them to a number of muons on the ground which corresponded exactly to the number of muons which would be surviving if

they had been created at the height of 2000 m and if their clock was slowed down accordingly to the Einstein Special Relativity theory.

But there are no article, in the scientific literature, that analyzed the credibility of these results and we can wonder if somebody ever asked himself this question. It is surprising, especially since this experiment is taught in all universities in the world.

This major experiment should be analyzed without preconceived ideas. If it is valid, undoubtedly, it is a demonstration of the validity of Einstein Special Relativity theory. The proof the authors are looking for in this experiment is to show, that if there is still muons at ground level, then it is due to Einstein SR theory. Due to the fact that muons lifetime could be increased, because of their high speed and according to Einstein SR theory, then muons could reach the earth floor, which they could not do otherwise. However, in order to be true they should have demonstrated that cosmic rays, which are creating muons, could not penetrate Earth atmosphere under 2 km altitude.

3 Cosmic Rays Penetration

To understand why there is still cosmic rays at ground level, and then can give muons at this height, it is necessary to have a look at the physics [2].

Electrically charged particles, like cosmic rays, have difficulty to enter the atmosphere as they tend to be deflected away by the geomagnetic field of the Earth. The ability of a cosmic particle to penetrate the atmosphere depends upon its own magnetic rigidity, which depends in particular to its momentum (speed).

In addition, at each altitude of the atmosphere, at a certain latitude, there is a minimum magnetic rigidity necessary for the particle to pursue its trajectory down to the ground, called the “cut-off” rigidity. When the particle has a lesser rigidity than the cut-off rigidity of the atmosphere at a certain altitude and latitude, it will be deviate north and will not attain the ground level at this latitude. Because the cut-off rigidity is inversely proportional to the square of the Earth geocentric radius, the cut-off rigidity rise when altitude decreases.

Then it is evident that close to ground level, only high velocity particles can attain these heights, those who are creating muons. It is what we can see on the graph of fig. 20 of reference [3]. Moreover, in this graph, it is shown that between 2 km and the ground, the number of cosmic particles decreases by only 20%! Then, this number indicates that there is almost no reduction of the concentration of high velocity particles between 2 km and the ground, those particles which are creating muons. I let the reader conclude by himself.

It is exactly what the authors measured! They mentioned they have measured 75 000 cosmic rays per hour at the level of Mount Washington and 68 400 cosmic rays per hour at ground level. The reader must take heed that the authors gave these data in a way such that the reader can't get it; data at Mount Washington are given in cosmic rays per hour whereas data at ground level are given in cosmic rays per seconds!

4 Conclusion

Knowing that in the range of altitudes in the D. Frisch experiment, velocity of cosmic rays are almost the same between 2 km and the ground, due to their magnetic rigidity, then there should be almost the same rate of atmospheric muons created by the penetrating cosmic rays at these two altitudes. It is exactly what the authors measured! Then why the author says that the presence of muons at ground level was due to Einstein Special Relativity theory?

The authors worried about the problem of penetrating cosmic rays in this range of altitudes, like they said it could question totally the conclusions! They evacuated this problem by indicating that studies

have shown that there was no creation of muons in the portion of height between 2 km and the ground, but giving no reference in their document! It is however the major point of the experiment.

On internet, we can see that 100 % of the articles on this experiment resume the David H. Frisch et James H. Smith conclusions without ever raising the elementary question of the validity of the time dilation of atmospheric muons assertion by looking to the physics of atmospheric muons creation. It is dismaying.

This experiment shows that there is no time dilation for high velocity particles such as atmospheric muons entering the Earth atmosphere and in consequence it is not a validation of Einstein Special Relativity theory.

References

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- [3] <https://cds.cern.ch/record/557167/files/p41.pdf>